

THE CHANGES IN UNITED STATES FOREIGN AID UNDER THE D. EISENHOWER ADMINISTRATION

Mustaqimov Firdavs Furqat o'g'li

Student of World Economy and Diplomacy University.

+998930833863

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Annotation: The article is devoted to the study of the peculiarities of the process of formation of the post-war world economic order during the administration of D. Eisenhower, within which contradictions were growing within the American ruling elite on the direction of US foreign economic policy. Special attention is paid to the study of ideological approaches to the foreign aid program of various groups of interests in the American Congress and administration.

Keywords: D. Eisenhower administration, world order, foreign aid, interest groups, progressives, traditionalists.

The construction of a post-war new world order, the strategic goal of which was "globalization in the American way", required the US leadership to use a fairly wide range of foreign policy tools - military force, diplomacy, propaganda apparatus, economic assistance. The latter, it seems, performed the main constructive role, and all the others were more of an auxiliary nature.

As you know, the first to include aid in the US foreign policy arsenal as an "advanced" tool was President G. Truman. The Truman Doctrine, the Marshall Plan and the "item-4" program became the main stages of this process. However, the use of this tool turned out to be such an expensive "pleasure" and caused such fierce resistance from the conservative, mostly republican opposition within the American elite that the administration had to abandon arguments related to the need for "recovery and development" of other countries. It turned out to be possible to press the necessary financing of external assistance only under the "smoke screen" of the Cold war. At the conceptual level, this was expressed in the complete dominance of the foreign policy doctrine of "mutual security" over the concept of "development assistance" immediately after the outbreak of the Korean War¹.

Although these two approaches began to compete with each other during the presidency of G. Truman, the battle between them acquired a truly epic character after the arrival of Republican D. Eisenhower in the White House. Agreeing to become a presidential candidate from the Republican Party, General Eisenhower sincerely shared the conservative ideals of his party members - classical economics, balanced budget, minimal government spending, etc. During the election campaign, the General repeatedly confirmed his desire to extend

these principles to the American foreign economic policy. And this was a natural intention, taking into account the fact that it was the internationalist wing of the Republican Party, consisting of representatives of progressives and corporate traditionalists, that was behind his nomination and election.

Using the issue of foreign aid as the most important tool of his pre-war struggle for the White House, General Eisenhower was able to give hope to both major groups in the Republican Party. On the one hand, he hinted to isolationists that he would completely eliminate external aid, and, on the other hand, promised internationalists to reorient it from military "deterrence" to economic globalization. However, after becoming president, Eisenhower was in no hurry to fulfill his promises. During his first year in the White House, he followed the course of his predecessor to use American aid to strengthen the Western-European economies and the military "containment" of communism in Europe, which caused discontent among all business groups and their representatives in the administration and Congress.² Nevertheless, the president was secretly preparing a change of course in the field of aid. From the predominance of the doctrine of "mutual security", focused on a black-and-white vision of the world, where there should be only friends or enemies, he planned to move on to strengthening the concept "development assistance" aimed at global integration into the Western economic system of not only friendly, but also neutral countries, as well as those that were behind the "iron" or "bamboo" curtain. Already in 1953, the President began to prepare the foundation for a strategic turn in the sphere of not only foreign aid, but also foreign economic policy in general. First of all, this concerned personnel policy – all the top foreign economic posts in the Eisenhower administration were occupied by representatives of two of the most influential internationalist business groups – progressive and traditionalist. In addition, one of the most influential political heavyweights and radical progressives, Harold Stassen, was appointed head of the Mutual Security Agency (MSA), inherited from the previous administration. Stassen immediately initiated the process of reorganizing the entire aid structure in order to redirect it to solving the problems of economic globalization.

As a result, the External Operations Administration (FOA) was created instead of the Mutual Security Agency. The new structure appeared to be more centralized and manageable, which allowed the administration to begin shifting a number of accents within the framework of the "mutual security" program (MSP) - from short-term security tasks to long-term economic development goals, from

military programs to civilian ones, from Europe to Asia, from grants to loans, from small technical assistance projects for large-scale economic planning. At the level of individual recipient countries, the focus was shifted from the principle of "urgent needs" to national planning, which aimed to integrate Asian underdeveloped countries, regardless of their political orientation, into a new multi-state world order based on the economic principles of "specialization, standardization and simplification", which They have always been the essence of the American business system.

To prevent an uprising in the camp of deceived radical opponents of aid, Eisenhower again promised them that by the middle of 1955 FOA and large-scale economic assistance will be abolished, and the remaining types of assistance will be transferred to the relevant ministries – the State Department or the Ministry of Defense. The real intentions of the administration's leaders in relation to the new mechanism of external assistance became clear only in 1954, after the President rejected the concept of forceful military "rejection". The report of the Randall Commission divided MSP conceptually into two parts: military, which continued to "restrain communism", and economic, within which a small sector of "development assistance" was created, reoriented to the tasks of economic development of Asian countries on the basis of cheap technical assistance. At that time, it was impossible to carry out a larger-scale "development assistance" through the congress, since the communist military threat was assessed as more serious than the Soviet economic expansion in the region. Having spent almost the whole of 1954 debugging the administrative mechanism of FOA, Stassen eventually managed to increase its effectiveness and attract many legislators to his side. In addition, in a fierce struggle within the administration, the director of the agency was able to overcome the extremely cautious trends in aid policy initiated by Randal, and boldly proposed a rather radical MSP bill for 1954 for consideration by Congress. The bill provided for a serious redistribution of aid funds in favor of the economic component and the Asian region as a whole, and also maintained the segment of the most criticized "development assistance". Moreover, by offering to support some neutral countries, the bill questioned the absoluteness of the "black-and-white" ideology of "mutual security". Since the united opposition subjected the draft to fierce criticism, the President was forced to intervene to soften the excessive progressive accents of the bill and find a basis for compromise. However, the catastrophe that the French fell into in Vietnam in August 1954, and the subsequent anti-communist hysteria in the United States gave the president an

excuse to reject the compromise already reached, restore the reduced funds and openly declare his support for Stassen's efforts to create a permanent core "development assistance" inside MSP. Although the administration did not officially explain how it was going to use the development assistance funds in Asia, the pro-progressive media immediately launched a propaganda campaign calling for the use of the Marshall Plan methodology to resolve the catastrophic situation in Southeast Asia. The main idea of the new "Marshall Plan for Asia" (PMA) was to restore the economy of the region with Japan as a "motor" and use local markets and sources of raw materials for Western European countries. This would allow the United States to reduce European pressure on the American market and restore the functioning of the "triangle" of world trade. Although Stassen and even the Secretary of State himself tried to find arguments in favor of the absolute importance of the PMA in the fact that the Soviet Union shifted the main emphasis in its global "communist plan" from a military to an economic offensive, almost no one at that moment believed in it. As a result, attempts to pass the PMA through the administration and Congress in 1954 met fierce resistance. Nevertheless, being under the strongest pressure from the President, the conservative opposition agreed to a minimum three-year PMA, for which only \$ 200 million was allocated. in exchange for the elimination of FOA and its militant director. For the legislative process, the idea of the PMA was formulated in detail in the so-called "Arches of Free Asia" (AFAP) plan. This plan, in accordance with the compromise, pointed to the need to "restrain" not Moscow, but Beijing as a regional superpower in South and Southeast Asia, and also foresaw the strengthening of Japan's role by reducing aid to Western Europe. In the spring of 1955, again in accordance with the above compromise, President Eisenhower dismissed G. Stassen, temporarily appointing him to the post of Secretary for Armament, after which he stated that from July 1 of the same year FOA was liquidated. However, in parallel with the liquidation of the old structure, a new external assistance agency was created - the International Cooperation Administration (ICA). To reduce the heat of indignation at such an unexpected turn, the president included ICA in the structure of the State Department and appointed conservative politician John Holister as the agency's rector.

Although Eisenhower "passed his half of the way", in the end he did not receive the PMA even in a stripped-down form, since the first preparatory step for its implementation led to disaster. In May 1955, at a conference in Simla (India), the Asian participating countries almost unanimously rejected the multilateral

regional principle of AFAP in order to preserve bilateral American aid, which seemed to them more profitable, at least in the short term. After becoming director, J. Holister tried to develop the offensive of the traditionalist-conservative group (the so-called "club 4-N") in the administration. Having publicly declared his loyalty to the presidential strategy of "mutual security", including the recent shift of emphasis towards the policy of "helping development", he actually began the liquidation of the entire progressive legacy of Stassen. Having taken steps towards a sharp reduction in the MSP budget, he at the same time actively used the program's resources to promote the interests of commodity corporations with the help of the development of a system of guarantees, the distribution of contracts in favor of their business proteges.

In the autumn of 1955, in an attempt to weaken this frightening trend, the progressive part of the administration, i.e. the so-called "young rock" group (N. Rockefeller, R. Nixon, G. Stassen and Dr. M. Eisenhower), launched a counteroffensive. In an attempt to portray Soviet aid to some underdeveloped countries as the beginning of a new dangerous stage of communist aggression, they insisted on a general increase in MSP funds and a proportional component of "development assistance". However, the traditionalists easily neutralized this obviously artificial argument, calling Soviet aid a "bluff" and claiming that Moscow does not have the necessary resources for large-scale foreign economic programs. However, unexpectedly, the "Young Turks" received support from the Soviet leadership, which in November 1955 began an active campaign for the provision of assistance to the USSR to some countries of South Asia. Taking advantage of the moment, the pro-progressists in the administration managed to consolidate their ranks and, with the help of the president, inflicted serious damage on the conservatives from the 4-N club. As a result, Congress approved a request for a "mutual security" program, which grew sharply from the \$2.7 billion requested by J. Holister, up to \$4.9 billion. However, immediately after this victory, which promised a lot of money, the progressive camp split into several groups. The "multi-sided" progressives wanted to send the maximum possible part of the aid through the UN channels.

The "moderate" wing of the Dulles group supported the need to use "development assistance" to implement a long-term strategy of economic "rejection" of communism in Eastern Europe and underdeveloped countries, but without forgetting about the construction of a "reliable military shield", i.e. implying a "balanced" approach to military and economic providing external assistance programs. The group of "radicals", headed by N. Rock-feller and Ch.

Jackson, believed that the "military shield" had already been built, and a Soviet military offensive seemed unlikely. Therefore, it was supposed to support only the general functionality of the "shield". Economic growth and rising living standards were to become the main weapon in the fight against communism and nationalism in the process of building a world order. Accordingly, the "radicals" demanded a sharp increase in "development assistance" by reducing military aid. Although at that time the "radicals" were poorly represented in the administration (especially after the resignation of N. Rockefeller), their positions were very actively supported by the powerful Fulbright-Kennedy Senate faction, as well as influential liberal intellectuals from the CENIS group, who continued to popularize their "world economic plan" and the theory of "self-sustaining growth". Despite the difference of views on the long-term strategic goals of aid, the "radicals" and the "moderates" had the same short-term task, namely to support and push the MSP sector, which was aimed at "development assistance". In their attempts to pass this concept through Congress in the framework of the 1956 MSP they launched an unprecedented campaign aimed at convincing the public that only massive "development assistance" could stop the "economic offensive" organized by Soviet leader N. S. Khrushchev. Since at that moment no one dared to call it a "bluff", the legislators agreed with the statement of the problem.

After Eisenhower was re-elected president in November 1956, and the Democrats, who generally supported the transformation of power, triumphantly won the congressional elections, the president began to get rid of the leading members of the administration who were members of the conservative "4-N club", which once again confirmed his progressive orientation. In July 1957, under severe political pressure from progressives and former conservative associates, J. was forced to resign. Holister. Having received the main management levers in the administration, the "moderate-radical" bloc developed a compromise strategy of "small steps". It implied the slow development of the core of "development assistance" within MSP through the creation of a revolving Development Loan Fund (DLF). The Fund had to be able to borrow money directly from the Treasury and thus could avoid the process of annual approval of appropriations in Congress. Although the legislators did not accept this idea and sharply reduced aid funds, the core of the DLF was a spa hay with the assistance of the Fulbright-Kennedy Senate group, which, in turn, believed that the White House was not persistent enough in implementing the

"development assistance" strategy. In any case, we can assume that from this moment the era of "development assistance" actually began.

The new director of the ICA, James Smith, a former military pilot and Assistant Secretary of the Navy (1953-1956), was considered a reliable supporter of Eisenhower's progressive line. Being a firm Republican, he tried to solve the problems of foreign aid professionally, pragmatically, avoiding political intrigues. Since he was warmly supported even by Democrats, he got the opportunity to lead the ICA on a truly "bipartisan" course. As a talented administrator, Smith, having given freedom of action to his experienced deputies (D. Fitzgerald, L. Sacchio and J. Oli), was able to significantly improve the work of the assistance mechanism and initiate reforms within ICA14. Despite his titanic efforts and obvious successes, criticism of the ICA was growing both in Congress and in society, which was very painful for the media. Having not received the expected promotion through the Pentagon, he resigned and left the government despite the president's desire to keep him as head of the agency.

The last year of Eisenhower's presidency was marked by deteriorating conditions for the development of the aid program. The upcoming elections, the economic crisis, the catastrophic deficit of the foreign trade balance, rising inflation, the leakage of gold from the country - all these factors stimulated, on the one hand, the general criticism of the presidential "balanced" approach in the field of aid, and on the other- "radicalism" of the Fulbright-Kennedy group. In order to weaken this untimely trend, the administration was forced to thoroughly rationalize the MSP program. Rationalization included the intensification of the multi-national and regional aspects of foreign aid, which could support the process of mobilizing and concentrating the resources of allies and recipients on solving critical problems in the most important underdeveloped countries, including neutral ones.

Forming the infrastructure of this policy, the administration proposed such initiatives as the development of a regional UN program for the development of the Middle East, the creation of an International Development Association, as well as the Inter-American Development Bank and a special consortium to rescue the Indian second five-year plan. Promoting these initiatives within the framework of the MSP for 1959, the strategists of the State Department decided to change the principles of power distribution. The main efforts to introduce "development assistance" were aimed at two regions that were supposedly "ripe" and met the criteria of the "big push": the Indus Basin (India and Pakistan) and Taiwan. Other recipients had to go through the preparation phase

for the "big push", using low-cost American technical assistance programs, primarily within the framework of the concept of "community development". A suitable figure for the leadership of the ICA and the implementation of such a program has finally been found. True, former diplomat James Ridleberger had never dealt with external power, but he was politically acceptable even for such an irreconcilable leader of the opposition in Congress as Otto Pasman. The new Director concentrated all his efforts on getting the new MSP through Congress, leaving the ICA leadership to his deputies. In general, while frequent changes of the head of the aid agency were clearly a weakening factor in the program, a permanent team of deputies who worked continuously from 1953 to 1961 was able to stabilize the functioning of the program and ensure its continuity. It should also be noted that each new stage in the development of the assistance program required the emergence of a new type of leader: Stanley Andrews was a professional manager, Harold Stassen was a politician, John Holister was a businessman and millionaire, James Smith was a soldier and, finally, James Ridleberger was a diplomat. Thus, comparing the foreign aid policy of the two American administrations – G. Truman and D. Eisenhower – it can be concluded that progressives who sought to move towards economic globalization through the use of centralized public-state planning tools, primarily external assistance, and minimized the role of private-enterprise activity, prevailed in both parties. However, progressives in the Democratic Party had a greater advantage than in the Republican Party, were more inclined to radical decisions in the field of aid, used Keynesian tools more actively, and did not hesitate to increase funding. Progressives-Republicans during the Eisenhower period were forced to adhere to their traditional conservative financial discipline, to a greater extent take into account the opinion of business circles and seek compromises with other factions in the party, which noticeably slowed down the progressive movement of the globalization process in the 1950s.

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